

Comparative Study of the Clinico-Radiological Outcomes of Fixation of Unstable Intertrochanteric Fractures with Standard Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN) and Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation for Asia (PFNA2)

Jayant Kumar Rai¹, Amresh Kumar², Vaishnavi Dutta Mishra³

¹Associate Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Rohtas, India

²Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Rohtas, India

³Assistant Professor, Department of Orthopaedics, Narayan Medical College & Hospital, Jamuhar, Sasaram, Rohtas, India

Received: 25-07-2024 / Revised: 23-08-2024 / Accepted: 25-09-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Amresh Kumar

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Introduction: Intertrochanteric fractures are common in elderly individuals with osteoporosis, where surgical fixation is crucial for reducing complications and promoting early mobilization. Proximal femoral nails (PFN) have been widely used for unstable intertrochanteric fractures, but complications such as screw cut-out and rotational instability persist. The PFNA2, featuring a helical blade, has been developed to improve fixation in osteoporotic bone by enhancing stability.

Materials and Methods: A prospective comparative study was conducted on 50 patients with unstable intertrochanteric fractures (AO 31.A2 and 31.A3). Group A (n=25) underwent surgical fixation using PFN, while Group B (n=25) received PFNA2. Patients were followed for six months, with clinical outcomes assessed using the Harris Hip Score and radiological outcomes by bone union time. Both groups had similar demographic and fracture characteristics.

Results: The mean age of patients was 60.75 years in Group A and 64.37 years in Group B. PFNA2 showed a significantly faster mean union time (14.69 weeks) compared to PFN (18.47 weeks). Harris Hip Scores improved significantly in both groups over time, with better results in PFNA2 group. Complications were lower in the PFNA2 group as well.

Conclusion: PFNA2 demonstrated superior clinico-radiological outcomes and fewer complications compared to PFN for unstable intertrochanteric fractures, suggesting it may be a better implant choice, particularly in osteoporotic patients.

This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.

Introduction

Intertrochanteric fractures of the femur commonly arise in older adults affected by weakened bone density. Prolonged inactivity after a hip fracture is linked to a higher mortality risk in this population. Consequently, surgical intervention has emerged as the favoured approach for ensuring correct fracture alignment and promoting early mobility in patients with osteoporosis [1]. Ensuring stable fixation is crucial in these situations, as implant failure can lead to serious consequences, and conducting revision surgeries is particularly risky due to the patients' compromised health. Consequently, investigators have been persistently exploring the most efficient devices for guaranteeing long-lasting stability in these types of fractures.

The dynamic hip screw has long been recognised as the standard approach for stable fractures; however, it falls short of effectively addressing unstable

intertrochanteric fractures [2]. For these more intricate fractures, employing intramedullary nails alongside dynamic stabilisation devices for the femoral head and neck has emerged as the favoured method [3]. Different nail designs, utilising either a single compression screw or a mix of compression and anti-rotation screws, like the PFN, have become increasingly popular in addressing unstable fractures. Although the PFN demonstrates greater efficacy compared to extramedullary devices in managing unstable fractures, challenges such as screw cut-out, back-out, varus collapse, and rotational instability continue to be significant concerns, with complication rates reported as high as 31% in certain studies [4].

The PFNA2 was developed to enhance stabilisation through the use of a single helical blade instead of a screw for securing the femoral head and neck. This

instrument is engineered to improve the connection between bone and implant while compressing cancellous bone, leading to enhanced stability in fixation [5]. The design allows for insertion without the need to remove bone from the head or neck fragment, enhancing stability, especially in cases of weakened bone structure. Biomechanical research has demonstrated that this helical blade, using bone compaction, provides enhanced resistance to rotational movements and varus collapse [6]. This prospective study seeks to assess and contrast the clinical and radiological results, along with the complications, linked to the application of PFN and PFNA2 in managing unstable intertrochanteric fractures.

Materials and Methodology:

This study, designed with a prospective and comparative approach, included 50 participants who were randomly divided into two groups of 25 individuals each. Group A comprised individuals with intertrochanteric fractures who underwent surgical intervention using a Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN), whereas Group B consisted of those who received treatment with the Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation (PFNA2). All participants were fully developed and presented with unstable intertrochanteric AO 31.A2 and 31.A3 fractures, fulfilling the established inclusion criteria. The criteria encompassed individuals aged 18 and older, who gave informed consent, presenting with closed, unstable intertrochanteric fractures and without any known comorbid conditions. Individuals under 18 years, those who did not provide consent, patients with compound or stable intertrochanteric fractures, and individuals with comorbidities like diabetes mellitus or hypertension were not included in the study. Follow-up assessments were carried out for a minimum of six months for all individuals, and the results were analysed and compared.

Upon admission, the primary approach involved implementing skin traction along with providing supportive care. After achieving anaesthetic clearance, the patients were readied for the surgical procedure. Consent was secured, and spinal anaesthesia was provided. The individual was placed on a traction table, and the alignment of the fracture was verified using fluoroscopy. The

surgical intervention was the same for both cohorts, differing only in the type of implant utilised and its particular application. Following meticulous cleaning, application of paint, and preparation of the area, an incision measuring roughly 3 cm was created 2-3 cm above the tip of the greater trochanter of the femur. The Tensor Fascia Lata was carefully incised to reveal the trochanteric area, which was verified through fluoroscopy. A curved awl was subsequently employed to establish an entry point located medial to the tip of the greater trochanter, followed by the insertion of a guide wire across the fracture site under fluoroscopic guidance. Proximal reaming was conducted, and either a PFN or PFNA2 was inserted through the reamed canal utilising a jig.

A secondary incision, roughly 3 cm long, was performed at the proximal locking location. A guide wire was placed in both anteroposterior (AP) and lateral views, ensuring a Tip Apex Distance (TAD) of 20 mm, with the wire terminating just proximal to the subchondral bone of the femoral head. In the PFN group, reaming was conducted using 8 mm and 6.4 mm reamers, while entry through the lateral cortex was achieved with a lateral cortex opener in the PFNA2 group, followed by reaming procedures. In the PFN group, screws for lag and de-rotation were measured and inserted with precise sizing. In the PFNA2 group, a correctly sized helical blade was secured to an impactor, advanced through careful tapping, and fixed in position with clockwise turns. Following the placement of the implant, distal locking was executed, and the final reduction of the fracture was verified using fluoroscopy. The injury was carefully cleaned, and the closure was executed in layers with a sterile dressing applied.

Individuals from both cohorts were released following the removal of sutures on the 12th day after surgery. Follow-up appointments were arranged for 3 weeks, 3 months, and 6 months after the procedure. During each appointment, individuals received a thorough clinical assessment and imaging analysis. Patient outcomes were evaluated through the Harris Hip Score, while imaging results were determined by the duration to union, indicated in weeks. Furthermore, any complications that occurred in either group were recorded and examined.

Figure 1: Post-op X-ray film of patient managed with standard PFN

Figure 2: Post-op X-ray film of another patient managed with standard PFN

Figure 3: Post-op X-ray film of patient managed with PFNA2.

Result

The average age of individuals in Group A was 60.75 ± 8.40 years, whereas in Group B, it was 64.37 ± 4.58 years. The mean age between the two groups showed no statistically significant difference ($p=0.059$). In Group A, 65% of individuals experienced their injury due to a straightforward fall, while 35% were associated with a vehicular incident. In Group B, 70% of the injuries were caused by a straightforward fall,

whereas 30% were attributed to road traffic incidents. In terms of fracture patterns, 70% of individuals in Group A presented with A2 fractures, while 30% exhibited A3 fractures. In contrast, Group B showed that 65% had A2 fractures and 35% had A3 fractures. The analysis revealed no notable differences in fracture patterns among the groups ($p=0.736$) or in the length of the surgical procedure ($p=0.117$). The assessment of the Harris Hip Score was conducted and analysed between the two groups.

Although the scores indicated no notable variation at the 3-week follow-up, marked differences were

detected at the 3-month and 6-month follow-ups, as illustrated in Table 1.

Table 1: Harris Hip Score comparison between both groups

	Group A		Group B		Total		P value
	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	Mean	SD	
3 Weeks	62.41	2.14	68.74	1.67	65.57	1.81	0.493
3 Months	66.82	2.66	78.9	3.01	72.86	2.92	0.038
6 Months	76.23	3.18	88.57	2.24	82.4	2.63	0.014

Furthermore, the average duration for bone healing in Group A was 18.47 ± 2.52 weeks, whereas in Group B, it was 14.69 ± 3.27 weeks. In terms of complications, four patients experienced superficial infections—three from Group A and one from Group B—which were successfully treated with prolonged antibiotic therapy. No instances of the Z-effect or reverse Z-effect were noted. Furthermore, there were no instances of implant failure, screw dislodgment, or cut-out of screws or blades among the patients.

Discussion

At present, there is a consensus that internal fixation is the preferred approach for managing intertrochanteric fractures to minimise complications and improve patient outcomes. Nonetheless, the optimal approach and selection of implant for addressing intertrochanteric fractures continue to be a subject of discussion, given that every technique presents its own set of benefits and drawbacks. The Proximal Femoral Nail (PFN) has demonstrated significant effectiveness in managing unstable and reverse oblique fractures, owing to its capacity to enhance axial telescoping and rotational stability, serving as a load-sharing mechanism [7,8]. The AO/ASIF group subsequently refined the PFN into the PFNA to enhance both angular and rotational stability through the use of a single element. This intramedullary device features a helical blade instead of a screw, providing enhanced stability in the femoral head, and has undergone evaluation in clinical studies [9]. The Asia Proximal Femoral Nail Antirotation (PFNA2) was designed to cater to the unique anatomical characteristics of Asian patients, incorporating a mediolateral angle of 5° and a proximal diameter of 16.5 mm. This adjustment leads to an improved anatomical alignment, successfully minimising hoop stress in the femoral shaft, which has played a key role in significantly decreasing both intraoperative and postoperative diaphyseal fractures [10].

Biomechanical studies have shown that osteoporosis significantly contributes to screw migration in the proximal femur, heightening the risk of implant failure [11]. Research has indicated that there is a relationship between osteoporosis and less favourable results in intertrochanteric

fractures [12]. As a result, multiple approaches have been utilised to enhance stabilisation in intertrochanteric fractures associated with reduced bone density, such as the use of cement augmentation and advancements in implant design [13]. Mora A et al. conducted a comparison between the PFNA2 (helical blade) and the PFN, revealing a reduced occurrence of cut-out with the PFNA [14]. Choo SK et al. observed reduced postoperative sliding with the PFNA2 in comparison to the PFN [15]. Park JH et al. noted markedly improved social function scores, enhanced mobility scores, and reduced complication rates with helical blade nails [16]. Gardenbroek et al. conducted a study that revealed a notably increased risk of secondary late complications and reoperations associated with the PFN compared to the helical blade device [17]. Similarly, our research revealed enhanced clinical and radiological results in unstable intertrochanteric fractures treated with the PFNA2 compared to the conventional PFN.

Conclusion

This study illuminates how implant selection affects intertrochanteric fracture care and results. The PFNA2 is better than the PFN for treating unstable intertrochanteric fractures, according to the findings. Better clinical and radiological outcomes allow patients to return to regular life sooner. The complication rate is decreased, especially in severely osteoporotic bones. Unfortunately, no implant can fix poor fracture reduction or location. These findings need to be confirmed with more patients.

References

1. Babhulkar S. Management of trochanteric fractures. *Indian J Orthop.* 2006;40(4):210–18.
2. Zhang K, Zhang S, Yang J, Dong W, Wang S, Cheng Y, et al. Proximal femoral nail vs. dynamic hip screw in treatment of intertrochanteric fractures: a meta-analysis. *Med Sci Monit.* 2014; 20:1628–33.
3. Kulkarni GS, Limaye R, Kulkarni M, Kulkarni S. Intertrochanteric fractures. *Indian J Orthop.* 2006; 40:16–23.
4. Hohendorff B, Meyer P, Menezes D, Meier L, Elke R. [Treatment results and complications

- after PFN osteosynthesis] *Unfallchirurg*. 2005; 108(11):938. 940, 941-46 passim.
5. Raviraj A, Anand A, Chakravarthy M, Pai S. Proximal femoral nail antirotation (PFNA) for treatment of osteoporotic proximal femoral fractures. *Eur J Orthop Surg Traumatol*. 2012; 22:301–05.
 6. Strauss E, Frank J, lee J, Kummer FJ, Tejwani N. Helical blade versus sliding hip screw for treatment of unstable intertrochanteric hip fractures. *Biomech Eval Injury*. 2006; 37:984–89.
 7. Simmermacher RKJ, Ljungqvist J, Bail H, Hockertz T, Vochteloo AJH, Ochs U et al. The new proximal femoral nail anti-rotation (PFNA) in daily practice: results of a multicentre clinical study. *Injury*. 2008; 39(8):932-9.
 8. Williams WW, Parker BC. Complications associated with the use of the gamma nail. *Injury*. 1992; 23(5):291-2.
 9. Kuderna H, Böhler N, Collon DJ. Treatment of intertrochanteric and subtrochanteric fractures of the hip by the Ender method. *J Bone Joint Surg Am [Internet]*. 1976; 58(5):604-611.
 10. Li M, Wu L, Liu Y, Wang C. Clinical evaluation of the Asian proximal femur intramedullary nail anti-rotation system (PFNA-II) for treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. *Journal of Orthopaedic Surgery and Research*. London; 2014, 9.
 11. Cheema G, Rastogi A, Singh V, Goel S. Comparison of cut out resistance of dynamic condylar screw and proximal femoral nail in reverse oblique trochanteric fractures: -a biomechanical study. *Indian J Orthop*. 2012;46(3): 259–65.
 12. Akan K, Cift H, Ozkan K, Eceviz E, Tasyikan L, Eren A. Effect of osteoporosis on clinical outcomes in intertrochanteric hip fractures treated with a proximal femoral nail. *J Int Med Res*. 2011;39(3):857–65.
 13. Gupta RK, Gupta V, Gupta N. Outcomes of osteoporotic trochanteric fractures treated with cement-augmented dynamic hip screw. *Indian J Orthop*. 2012;46(6):640–45.
 14. Mora A, Marimon I, Rius M, Brill W, Corral A, Gaya S. PFN versus PFNA in treatment of trochanteric femoral fractures: A prospective study. *Bone and Joint Journal Orthopaedic proceedings*. 2011;93(2):136.
 15. Choo SK, Oh HK, Choi JY. PFNA and PFN in intertrochanteric fractures - comparison study of sliding. *J Korean Hip Soc*. 2010 Mar;22(1): 79–85.
 16. Park JH, Lee YS, Park JW, Wang JH, Kim JG. A comparative study of screw and helical proximal femoral nails for the treatment of intertrochanteric fractures. *Orthopaedics*. 2010 ;33(2):81–85.
 17. Gardenbroek T, Segers M, Simmermacher R, Hammacher E. The proximal femoral nail antirotation: an identifiable improvement in the treatment of unstable pertrochanteric fractures? *J Trauma*. 2011;71(1):169–74.